

A STOCHASTIC CUMULATIVE DAMAGE MODEL FOR THE FATIGUE RESPONSE OF LAMINATED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Polymer-matrix fibre-reinforced laminated composites display considerable variability in their fatigue response. Existing works on the quantification of fatigue response of composite laminates have deployed statistical and probabilistic approaches. These approaches are however inadequate for the prediction of the fatigue response as well as its probabilistic characteristics, and for the determination of reliability for use in design. In the present paper, a new cumulative damage model is developed based on a stochastic approach. The damage evolution in the composite laminate is quantified through the compliance increase in the laminate based on the embedded Markov process theory. The prediction of increase in compliance and the associated probabilistic characteristics is carried out based on this model. The fatigue response of a graphite epoxy composite laminate is then analyzed based on the new model using the test data. The composite material considered is AS 4/3501-6 graphite epoxy cross ply lay up $[0/90]_{4s}$.

KEYWORDS: fibre-reinforced polymer-matrix laminated composites, fatigue behaviour, stochastic process modelling and analysis, markov chains

INTRODUCTION

Laminated composites are known for the high degree of variability in their mechanical properties. In particular, the behaviour and engineering properties of polymer-matrix laminated composite materials are significantly affected by the technological process defects, design errors at both material and structural level, and environmental effects which are random in nature. However, for quantifying the fatigue behaviour of composite laminates, so far only a deterministic approach has in most cases been deployed. This deterministic approach has resulted in disagreement between theory and practice.

Weibull [1] introduced into fatigue failure studies a probability distribution function in order to account for the variations in the life data of mechanical components made of metallic materials. Reliability analyses have been developed for metallic structures based on this distribution function. The Weibull distribution function has also been used to model the fatigue life data of composites [2-4].

The Weibull distribution function frequently provides a reasonable fit to the probability distributions of life times that have been obtained from fatigue tests or service operation. Some aspects of variability in life time can be assessed and accounted for. However, (i) the probability distribution function of life times has not been related to the fatigue damage process, (ii) it is not possible to separate and account for the major sources of variability in material response, (iii) the

correlation characteristics of test data are not accounted for, and (iv) the nature of physical process is not reflected. Further, there are only two limiting states of the material in the Weibull distribution based fatigue model, that are (i) satisfactory (no damage) and (ii) failure (completely damaged). This imposes severe limitations on the validity and applications of this model. For instance, one can not incorporate the initial damage distribution (for a composite, this refers to the fluctuations in the initial elastic modulus) nor it is possible to trace the damage accumulation during service using the Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) techniques. A rigorous stochastic approach can take into account all sources of variability in material response and lead to a reliable prediction of material response.

Fundamental to the design of composite structures is a model that can be deployed for the prediction of fatigue damage accumulation. The development of a cumulative damage model based on a rigorous stochastic approach and the associated prediction scheme is the objective of the present work.

MARKOV PROCESS MODELLING OF COMPLIANCE

The model developed here considers the "Cumulative Damage (CD)" due to fatigue, which is the irreversible accumulation of fatigue damage in the composite material. A "Stochastic Phenomenological Model" is developed, since the experimental data display considerable randomness. The central idea is that in a suitably defined "Duty Cycle (DC)" a random amount of fatigue damage is accumulated in the composite laminate. This fatigue damage in turn results in the reduction of the elastic modulus of the laminate.

It is quite natural and reasonable to assume that the increment of damage at the end of a DC depends in a probabilistic manner on the amount of damage present at the start of the DC, on that DC itself, and is independent, in the probabilistic sense, of how (i.e. the damage development path) the damage was accumulated up to the start of that DC. This corresponds to the Markov assumption in the stochastic process theory.

It may be noted here that the Markov assumption is consistent with the system theory concepts that are well established. The laminate specimen can be viewed as a dynamic system. At any instant of time (or equivalently the load cycles), the compliance of the laminate is analogous to a variable system parameter. The input to the system, i.e. the excitation, is the loading during a DC. The increase in the compliance of the sample (i.e. damage increment) can be viewed as an output (i.e. response). The Markov assumption then simply implies that the response of the system (which is the increase in compliance at the end of a DC) is a function of the system parameter (i.e. the fatigue damage that has been present in the laminate before the DC was applied which is indicated by the laminate compliance at the start of the DC), and the excitation, and is independent of the way with which the value of the system parameter (i.e. the fatigue damage in the laminate at the start of DC) has been arrived at.

It is well known that (i) unlike the metals in a composite laminate various damage mechanisms become simultaneously active, and (ii) the viscoelastic response of the laminate is path-dependent. However, the fatigue damage in a laminate is not quantified in terms of the length of the fatigue crack or any other physically-observable variables (for which the path dependency is an important consideration) as in the case of metals. Rather, a material parameter such as compliance that is sensitive to, reflective of and representative of whatever forms of fatigue damage is deployed as a "system descriptor" or "damage development indicator". Also, this

parameter is determined from the instantaneous response of the laminate and not from the transient response.

Test data regarding the elastic modulus are collected using nominally-identical composite specimens that are subjected to fatigue loading. The compliance, which is the reciprocal of elastic modulus, increases as the fatigue damage sets in. The compliance is denoted here by C and the number of load cycles is denoted by n . The values of the stress ratio and the stress amplitude of the fatigue loading are denoted by R and S respectively.

For each test specimen, the $C - n$ curve can be plotted. Due to the inherent variability associated with the accumulated damage, this curve varies from specimen to specimen. Typical sample realizations are depicted in Figure 1. The stochastic process modelling the compliance is denoted as $\{C(n, S, R), n \in N, S \in A, R \in B\}$, where N, A and B are the respective sample spaces of the number of load cycles, the stress amplitude and the stress ratio. The sets N, A and B are the index sets of the stochastic process $\{C(n, S, R)\}$.

The discrete set of damage states is determined based on the following procedure. The entire range of compliance values is calculated from the sample test data. This range is then divided into m number of equal or non-equal intervals, $(C_2 - C_1), (C_3 - C_2), \dots, (C_{i+1} - C_i), \dots, (C_{m+1} - C_m)$, where C_{m+1} is the maximum value of the compliance.

Finite Markov Chain

The compliance process is viewed as a Markov process. The compliance process is non-homogeneous because the compliance is a continuous function of the number of load cycles. The index set N of this non-homogenous Markov process is $(n_0, n_1, n_2, \dots, n_{j-1}, n_j, \dots, n_{\max})$ and the state space is $(1, 2, 3, \dots, j-1, j, \dots, m)$. Both these index sets are discrete. A Markov process that has discrete index sets is called as Markov Chain (MC). Since the index sets are finite, the compliance becomes a Finite Markov Chain.

Transition Probability Function (TPF)

As a result of the Markovian property and non-homogeneity of the stochastic process,

$$p_{ij}(n_{k-1}, n_k) = P[C(n_j) = j | C(n_{j-1}) = i]; n_k \in n_{k-1} \quad (1)$$

where $p_{ij}(n_{k-1}, n_k)$ is the Transition Probability Function (TPF), which is the probability of the composite specimen entering a new damage state j at loading cycle n_k , given that it is currently in damage state i at loading cycle n_{k-1} . Based on the definition of the conditional probability density function, joint probability density function and Bayes' theorem [5] this equation can be recast into

$$p_{ij}(n_{k-1}, n_k) = P\{[C_j < C(n_k) \leq C_{j+1}] \cap [C_i < C(n_k) \leq C_{i+1}]\} / P[C_i < C(n_k) \leq C_{i+1}] \quad (2)$$

The individual probability density functions of random variables C_{k-1} and C_k are denoted by $f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1})$ and $f_{C_k}(c_k)$ respectively. The joint probability density function corresponding to these two

correlated random variables is denoted by $f_{C_{k-1} C_k} (c_{k-1}, c_k)$. The TPF between damage states i and j , can be determined according to

$$p_{ij} (n_{k-1}, n_k) = \int_{C_j}^{C_{j+1}} \int_{C_i}^{C_{i+1}} f_{C_{k-1} C_k} (c_{k-1}, c_k) dc_{k-1} dc_k / \{ \int_{C_i}^{C_{i+1}} f_{C_{k-1}} (c_{k-1}) dc_{k-1} \} \quad (3)$$

Transition Probability Matrix (TPM)

Generalizing Eq. (2) for all possible damage states included in the state space, the Transition Probability Matrix (TPM) of the composite specimen, denoted by $[[[(n_{k-1}, n_k)]]$, when the load cycle is increased from n_{k-1} to n_k , can be obtained. Since all damage states are mutually exclusive and collectively exhaustive, the sum of the probabilities in any row of the TPM that has non-zero probabilities is equal to unity. When the load cycle is n_{k-1} , the compliance is $C(n_{k-1}) = i$. Now, if the load cycle is increased to n_k , the compliance is $C(n_k) = j$. It is also possible that $C(n_k) = C(n_{k-1})$ so that $j = i$. However, the system can not make a transition from a higher state to a lower state, i.e. $C(n_k) < C(n_{k-1})$ so that $j < i$. The final state m is the "absorbing state" and so $p_{mm} (n_{k-1}, n_k) = 1$.

M-Step Transition Probability Matrix

The transition probability matrix of the composite specimen corresponding to any initial load cycle n_0 and any final load cycle n_m can be determined in terms of the transition probability matrices, based on the stochastic process theory. The resulting matrix of order $m \times m$ is called as the "M-Step Transition Probability Matrix (M-Step TPM)" and is denoted by $[[[(n_0, n_m)]]$. In order to determine this matrix, use is made of the Chapman-Kolmogorov Theorem [5]. The product equation for the M-Step TPM is obtained as

$$[[[(n_0, n_m)]] = [[[(n_0, n_1)]] \times [[[(n_1, n_2)]] \times [[[(n_2, n_3)]] \times \dots \times [[[(n_{m-1}, n_m)]] \quad (4)$$

In order to determine the unconditional probabilities of the damage states of the specimen, given the initial damage state distribution, when the load cycle is increased from n_0 to n_m , the following equation is derived.

$$\{ \prod^U (n_0, n_m) \} = \{ \prod (0) \} \times [[[(n_0, n_1)]] \times [[[(n_1, n_2)]] \times \dots \times [[[(n_{m-1}, n_m)]] \quad (5)$$

In this equation, $\{ \prod (0) \}$ denotes the initial damage state (row) vector of the specimen which consists of the probabilities of the specimen in different damage states at load cycle n_0 .

Prediction of Damage States at any Load Cycle

The initial and final values of load cycles that have been included in the test program are first considered. This duty cycle is expressed in terms of m number of smaller duty cycles. For each smaller duty cycle, the transition probability matrix is determined according the procedure given in the foregoing. This way, m number of transition matrices will be available. For each entry in the transition probability matrix, m number of values will be available. For instance, consider any transition probability p_{ij} . If 10 steps (smaller duty cycles) are considered, ten values of this transition probability viz., $1p_{ij}, 2p_{ij}, 3p_{ij}, \dots, 10p_{ij}$ will be available. These ten values are considered as constituting a random variable. Further, it is assumed here that this random variable, denoted by p_{ij} has a Gaussian distribution.

The ten sample values are used as a basis for predicting the value of transition probability p_{ij} that corresponds to the duty cycle defined by the final load cycle value of the 10-th (smaller) duty cycle and the value of the load cycle at which the prediction is to be made. The relevant rationale and procedure are outlined in the following.

(i) For the random variable p_{ij} , a Gaussian probability density function is fitted using the ten sample values available. The parameters of this Gaussian density function, μ_{ij} and σ_{ij} , can be determined following the standard parameter estimation techniques [6]. A suitable statistical analysis program is available in the MATLAB software, and this program was used in the present work.

(ii) A standardized random variable z_{ij} is defined according to the relationship $z_{ij} = (p_{ij} - \mu_{ij}) / \sigma_{ij}$. This standardized random variable will also have Gaussian distribution because the Gaussian nature of probability distribution does not change when a linear transformation of normal random variable is performed.

(iii) Now, the concepts of reliability theory and failure probabilities [7] are deployed. It can be proved using the probability theory and system reliability theory that a value of p_{ij} that corresponds to a reliability R (say 90%) can be obtained by first determining the value of z_{90} such that the area bounded by the density function curve of z_{ij} between the range $-\infty$ to z_{90} is 0.9, and then calculating the value of p_{ij} according to the relationship $(z_{90} \sigma_{ij}) + \mu_{ij}$. For instance, when the reliability is 90%, the value of z_{90} is approximately equal to 1.3. Now consider a transition probability, say p_{33} . By fitting a Gaussian distribution, the parameters of Gaussian density function for p_{33} can be obtained and say, they are equal to, 0.4819 and 0.2843 (it is worthwhile to note the magnitude of randomness in the values of p_{33} , which is approximately 60% in the above example). The value of p_{33} which will have a reliability of 90% (i.e. the probability that this value will be exceeded in actual test results is 10%) is $\{[1.3 (0.2843)] + 0.4819\}$ which is equal to 0.8515. This is the predicted value of p_{33} . This procedure is followed to determine the predicted values of all the transition probabilities. This way, the complete transition probability matrix is determined.

Now, the (10+1) - step duty cycle defined by the initial value of the load cycle in the test program and the value of the duty cycle at which the prediction is to be made, is considered. Ten transition probability matrices can be determined from test data and the eleventh transition probability matrix is predicted. The unconditional probabilities of damage states corresponding to the load cycle at which prediction is to be made can be determined using Eqs. (4) and (5). The value of m is equal to 11. These unconditional probabilities define the histogram of damage states corresponding to the load cycle where prediction is to be made.

Analytical Probability Density Functions

The probability density function of the compliance at load cycle n_{k-1} , which is denoted as $f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1})$ is determined based on the Maximum Entropy Method [7]. Based on this method, the analytical form of the probability density function $f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1})$ is taken to be

$$f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1}) = \exp \left[\lambda_0 + \sum_{i=1}^p \lambda_i c_{k-1}^i \right] \quad (6)$$

The values of the parameters λ_i , $i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, p$ are determined such that the entropy of the random variable c_{k-1} given by

$$S = - \int_R f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1}) \ln [f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1})] dc_{k-1} \quad (7)$$

where R denotes the range of the random variable c_{k-1} , is maximum, subject to the following constraints: (i) the total probability is unity, i.e.

$$\int_R f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1}) dc_{k-1} = 1 \quad (8)$$

and (ii) the probabilistic moments of the random variable c_{k-1} defined in terms of the probability density function $f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1})$ are equal to the corresponding statistical moments obtained from the compliance data, i.e.

$$\int_R c_{k-1}^i f_{C_{k-1}}(c_{k-1}) dc_{k-1} = M_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, q \quad (9)$$

where M_i is the i -th statistical moment about the origin of the compliance values c_{k-1} .

Further details regarding the Maximum Entropy Method can be found in Ref. 7. The above problem should be solved based on the techniques of optimization. The optimization technique that is best suited to this problem is the Nonlinear Programming Technique proposed by Jacobson and Oksman [8].

Joint Probability Density Functions

The joint probability density function is determined based on the relative frequency approach [6], in the form of a three-dimensional histogram.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

The composite material considered is AS 4/3501-6 Graphite Epoxy cross ply lay up $[0/90]_{4s}$. Plates made up of this material and of dimensions 280 mm x 250 mm x 1 mm were manufactured. The manufacturing conditions are as follows: Each plate is first heated for 1 hour at a temperature of 116° C and at a pressure of 586 kPa (full vacuum), then it is heated for 2 hours at a temperature of 176° C and at a pressure of 655 kPa (full vacuum). Each plate was then used to produce 10 specimens each of dimensions 280 mm x 25 mm x 1 mm. Aluminium plates 30 mm x 30 mm x 0.2 mm were attached to the gripping regions of the specimens, using the ASTM D 3039/D 3039-93 test procedure. The effects of relaxation stresses induced during manufacturing usually disappear about six months after fabrication, as described in [9]. In order to minimize the effects of stress relaxation, all the tests for a batch of specimens were carried out at a fixed time, that is one month after conditioning, after which 90% of the recovery has taken place.

The environmental conditions can seriously affect the damage properties of composites. In particular, the internal stress caused by machining and the moisture induced during machining can change the value of the damage measure, and so the specimens must be conditioned before testing. The method previously used in Ref. 9 has been employed in the present work, in this regard. It consists of (i) heating the specimens at 100° C in an oven for 2 hours, (ii) raising the

temperature to 170° C and holding it for two hours, and (iii) leaving the specimen at room temperature for at least one week before testing. All the plates were tested for defects using C-scanning technique and using microscopic inspection for voids, and only those plates that met the required quality were chosen for static and fatigue tests.

Static Testing

In the experimental investigation, considerable attention has been paid to ensure the quality of the composite specimens and test procedures. Two specimens were chosen from each plate to be tested for static properties and strength, and those specimens were chosen from a random position in the plate. The specimens were tested for their tensile properties in accordance with the ASTM D 3039/D 3039-93 standard test method for tensile properties of polymer matrix composite materials. Only those plates with specimens having tensile strength and modulus within 10% variation of the average tensile strength and average modulus of all tested specimens, were accepted. All other specimens were rejected. The (statistical) average tensile strength of the tested specimens was 614 MPa with a standard deviation of 49.5 MPa. The (statistical) average Young's modulus of the tested specimens has been 61.151 GPa with a standard deviation of 2.27 GPa.

Fatigue Testing

Tests were conducted at room temperature on an MTS hydraulic machine. Specimens were clamped to the machine grips using Al tabs as outlined in the ASTM D 3039/D 3039-93 test procedure. An on-axis T-T fatigue load at 5 Hz frequency and with a load ratio R of 0.1 was applied. The maximum load is chosen to be that required to induce gradual failure to the specimens. The value chosen corresponds to 70% of the average specimen strength. This value represents a realistic value used in the design of composite structures. The fatigue/static strength ratio for uniaxial CFRP is widely quoted [10] as being about 70% for endurance of about 10^7 cycles. The stress level selected is at a middle level between the higher applied stress levels resulting in higher stiffness at failure and shorter fatigue lives, and the lower stress levels which induce more total damage than higher stress levels (as evident by the greater amount of stiffness reduction at failure). The fatigue modulus was obtained by dividing the maximum applied stress by the corresponding strain. The values were monitored continuously during load cycling. The values of fatigue compliance at different number of load cycles were plotted in Figure 1.

NUMERICAL RESULTS FOR THE MARKOV CHAIN

Step 1:Determination of the damage states: The largest value in the state space i.e. the largest value of the compliances of all test specimens, is $1.7831 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ and the lowest value is $1.6114 \times 10^{-11} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$, as can be seen from Figure 1. This range of compliance values is then divided into seventeen damage states of same size.

Step 2:Generate Probability Density Functions for Each Compliance Value Set $C(n_{k-1})$: The first four statistical moments, i.e. M_1 , M_2 , M_3 and M_4 , of each compliance value set $C(n_{k-1})$ are determined and are used as constraints in the determination of $f_{C_{k-1}}$. The maximum entropy method yields the values of the five parameters viz., λ_i , $i=0, 1, 2, \dots, 4$, for each $f_{C_{k-1}}$. The values of these parameters are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: List of the values of λ_i at five load cycles

	λ_0	λ_1	λ_2	λ_3	λ_4
0 cycle	-59.75927	12.11768	-0.976104	0.0350279	-0.000468
101 cycles	-52.95307	4.758957	-0.163753	0.0024078	-0.000013
151 cycles	-10.20866	0.032665	0.0168172	-0.000467	0.0000034
201cycles	11.63882	-1.913443	0.0765457	-0.001223	0.0000067
251 cycles	-1.021048	-0.437083	0.0163917	-0.000210	0.0000008

Step 3:Determination of Joint Probability Density Functions: Five three-dimensional histograms that correspond to five smaller duty cycles (0, 101), (101, 151), (151, 201), (201, 251) and (251, 301) are determined.

Step 4:Evaluation of Transition Probability Matrices: The transition probability matrices can now be evaluated using Eq. (3). The single-variable integration is performed using a subroutine available in MATLAB software. At this stage, the sum of the non-zero transition probabilities in each row of the transition probability matrix is calculated. Theoretically, the sum must be equal to unity. However, for practical purposes, a tolerance margin of $\pm 10\%$ is used in the present work. If the sum of the transition probabilities is more than 1.1 or less than 0.9, suitable modifications have to be made as to the bounding compliance values of the damage states C_i , $i = 1, 2, \dots, 18$ and/or the bounds used for the single-variable distributions. An iterative procedure is hence called for. The five transition probability matrices each of order 17×17 corresponding to the five duty cycles (0, 101), (101, 151), (151, 201), (201, 251) and (251, 301) are obtained using the above procedure. The matrices $[\Pi(0, 101)]$ and $[\Pi(101, 151)]$ are considered for illustrative purposes and those parts of the rows and columns of these matrices that have non-zero entries are given below:

$[\Pi(n_0, n_1)] = [\Pi(0, 101)]:$
 Row 1 0.0 0.4369 0.2496 0.1872 0.1248 0.0 0.0
 Row 2 0.0 0.2003 0.5342 0.1335 0.0668 0.0668 0.0

$[\Pi(n_1, n_2)] = [\Pi(101, 151)]:$
 Row 2 0.0 0.3064 0.7149 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
 Row 3 0.0 0.0 0.5243 0.5243 0.0 0.0 0.0
 Row 4 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.3935 0.5902 0.0 0.0
 Row 5 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.2792 0.5583 0.0
 Row 6 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.9089 0.0

Step 5:Calculation of m -step Transition Probability Matrices: The 5-step transition probability matrix $[\Pi(n_0, n_5)]$, which is $[\Pi(0, 301)]$ can be determined using Eq. (4). The entries in the first two rows and first six columns of the transition probability matrices have non-zero values and they are given below:

$[\Pi(n_0, n_5)] = [\Pi(0, 301)] =$
 Row 1 0.0 0.4369 0.2496 0.1872 0.1248 0.0
 Row 2 0.0 0.2003 0.5342 0.1335 0.0668 0.0668

Step 6: Calculation of the Unconditional Probabilities of Compliances at Load Cycle 301: This step is carried out using Eq. (5) to determine the probability density function of compliances at the end of duty cycle (0, 301). The row vector $\{\Pi(0)\}$ consists of the probability distribution of initial damage states of the specimens and is determined from the distribution of $C(0)$. For the present case the row vector $\{\Pi(0)\}$ is given by: $\{\Pi(0)\} = \{0.516129, 0.483871, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0\}$. The unconditional probabilities of the compliances at $n_5=301$ is given below:

$$\{\Pi^U(0, 301)\} = \{0.0 \ 0.0967 \ 0.0967 \ 0.3870 \ 0.2580 \ 0.1290 \ 0.0322 \ 0 \dots\dots 0\}$$

Prediction of Damage State Probabilities at Load Cycle 351

Now, the duty cycle (301, 351) is considered. Using the transition probability matrices $[\Pi(0, 101)]$, $[\Pi(101, 151)]$, $[\Pi(151,201)]$, $[\Pi(201, 251)]$, and $[\Pi(251, 301)]$, the transition probability matrix $[\Pi(301, 351)]$ is predicted with a reliability of 90%. All the non-zero transition probabilities are located within the first six rows and six columns of predicted matrix $[\Pi(251, 301)]$:

$[\Pi(301, 351)] :$

Row 1	0.0	0.3414	0.1950	0.1463	0.0975	0.0
Row 2	0.0	1.1415	0.7022	0.1043	0.0522	0.0522
Row 3	0.0	0.0	0.8515	0.6060	0.0	0.0
Row 4	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.0259	0.5545	0.0
Row 5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2590	0.4752
Row 6	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	1.2924

The unconditional probability matrix is given by $\{\Pi^U(0, 351)\} : \{0.0 \ 0.0709 \ 0.0965 \ 0.2989 \ 0.3494 \ 0.0899 \ 0.0944 \ 0 \ 0 \dots\dots 0\}$, and the corresponding histogram is plotted in Figure 2. From the test data, the histogram of compliances at load cycle 351 is determined (Figure 3). They are: $\{0.0 \ 0.0968 \ 0.0968 \ 0.3548 \ 0.2581 \ 0.0968 \ 0.0968 \ 0 \ 0 \dots\dots 0\}$. A reasonable agreement can be observed.

CONCLUSIONS

The fatigue behaviour of laminated composites is considered and a stochastic approach to model and analyze this behaviour is developed. The following major sources of variability in cumulative damage process are incorporated in the stochastic model: (i) Initial damage state, (ii) Severity and order of both the load cycles as well as the material damage, (iii) State of damage at the failure of the test specimen. The severity of load cycle and the material damage (including the changes in the material properties) is specified in the model in terms of the probability transition matrix. The variations in the severity of repetitive load cycles and the material damage are incorporated through the non-homogeneous nature of the damage evolution process. The randomness in the initial damage due to manufacturing errors, technological process defects, design errors etc., is specified by the initial damage state vector. The stochastic model developed in the present work possesses the capability of prediction.

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Fig. 1 Typical Sample Realizations of Specimen Compliance

Fig. 2 Predicted Probability Distribution for the Compliance at Load Cycle 351

Fig. 3 Histogram of the Compliance at Load Cycle 351